

**POLITENESS IN EFL CLASSROOM INTERACTIONS AND ITS IMPLICATIONS TOWARD
EFL TEACHING-LEARNING IN SMP NEGERI 2 TABANAN IN ACADEMIC YEAR
2013/2014**

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed at (1) analyzing the kinds of politeness strategies which were used in the classroom interaction by the grade-eight EFL teacher and students of SMP Negeri 2 Tabanan; (2) analyzing the kinds of instructional function implied in the politeness strategies used by the grade-eight EFL teacher and students of SMP Negeri 2 Tabanan in EFL classroom interaction; (3) investigating implication of the politeness strategies towards English teaching-learning process in SMP Negeri 2 Tabanan. The research was designed as a qualitative study. The data were taken from observed interactions in the teaching and learning process in the classroom and interview. The obtained data were in the form of utterances produced in classroom interactions. The utterances were identified and analyzed descriptively by using face saving theory in order to know the politeness strategy used by teacher and students. The analysis was continued by identifying and analyzing the functions which were included in the politeness strategies used by them by using speech act theory, and the last, it was continued by analyzing and discussing the implication of the politeness are occurred at the EFL classroom interaction. The result of the study show (1) politeness was conveyed through five strategies, namely; bald-on record, positive politeness, negative politeness, off record, and saying nothing; (2) the functions of the politeness can be divided into three, namely, expressive, directive, and representative function; (3) the implication of the politeness used at the EFL classroom interaction performs in five aspects where those aspects are very influenced in the process of teaching and learning. The five aspects are efficient teaching and learning, respect communication between teacher and students, togetherness between teacher and students, cooperating interaction between teacher and students, and the use of less imposition and indirectness expression. Those aspects can motivate students and also developing a meaningful teaching and learning process.

Keywords : politeness, politeness strategies, speech acts, and EFL classroom interaction.

INTRODUCTION

Language is a key point in human daily communication. It is formed by collection of sounds that can form a system and is used by people to interact in their societies known as system of sound. It conveys meaning and makes other

people know what other people say or express (Meyer, 2009).

Meaning should be thought by the people who are as receivers or interlocutors. The speakers will send their ideas to the hearers or interlocutors, and then the ideas will be thought by the

hearer as a meaning where both of the two people stay in a same condition and finally agreed in one field of meaning in a society (Morris, 2007).

Language and society are bounding each-other. Language used by people in certain places is concerned with social and cultural phenomena (Trudgill, 1983).

Moreover, Schiffrin (1994) believes that language is a system whose rules and norms cannot be separated from culture and the major source of culture is knowledge. It means that the language used in the society deals with the social values or social norms which are developed there. Language stays and walks together with culture that influences the language.

Moreover, Hymes (1994) states that language should be related with the place where and when that language is used. Therefore, people use the language based on social behavior agreed and accepted as their togetherness. In some situation, speakers are often difficult in transferring their ideas by good words which are easy to be understood by the hearer and have a good impact to the hearer (Svarova, 2008). Additionally, the speaker and hearer usually have different competencies in communication (Morris, 2007). In addition, Seken (2007) also believes that speaker usually found problem on how to cover or how to utter the ideas to the hearer in a good way and also it can be reserved. Thus, learners need knowledge of forms, meanings, and functions. However, they must also use this knowledge by taking into consideration the social situation in order to convey their intended meaning appropriately (Freeman, 2003).

The people live together in a society and do available conventions or norms in the social society where the politeness as a strategy to avoid conflict that might be happened and also in order to develop good relationship or togetherness in social interaction (Watts, 2003; Rash, 2004). It is very important if speaker uses politeness as strategy in order to communicate with other members of social community. Seken (2007) adds

that when talking about politeness in the communication, language will be as a behavior of the human in the social interaction. This should be related to the fact that the speech participants hold on politeness principle by showing good attitude towards speech partner (Seken, 2004).

By regarding the explanation, there are some different opinions or beliefs stated by the linguist who is concerned with politeness. Because of that, Fraser (1990) groups the linguists' theories that have been introduced in the world. There are four categories of politeness theory. The first is politeness theory that believes with the social norms. This theory concerns with habitual of the people as norms or convention in one place. The second one is politeness theory that believes relationship or togetherness as a principle in a communication. In this theory, speakers try to decrease the offended conflict with the hearer. The third type is politeness theory that believes about saving face. This theory emphasizes on saving the speaker's face is very important. Then the last is politeness strategy that believes with conversational contract. This theory believes that all of participants have prepared the contract which is obtained the obligations.

According to Lakoff (1973), politeness is a strategy used by the speaker to avoid conflict with the hearer. It means that problem can be found in a communication process because of different assumptions, conventions or others. As stated by Grice (1975), human communication should be explained as a form of social interaction whose success depends on the interactants' presumption that communicative behavior is driven by certain norms and rules. Moreover, Leech (1983) believes that communication should take care with the togetherness or good relationship. The three experts believe that politeness is a relationship principle or a principal of keeping togetherness in a communication in order to avoid offended conflict that might be happened.

On the contrary, Brown & Levinson (1987) have different assumption from those three experts. The assumption is concerned with face saving politeness which comprison a strategy to save the hearer's face by the speaker. The speaker does not want to threat the hearer face. This theory believes in some case there are utterances that threat the hearer's face (Face threatening acts).

In accordance to FTA, Yule (1996) gives the definition of face. According to Yule, face is the public self-image of a person. It refers to the emotional and social sense of self that everyone has and expects everyone else to recognize. Politeness in interaction can be defined as a means employed to show awareness of another person's face. In this sense, politeness can be accomplished in situations of social distance or closeness. Showing awareness for another person's face when that other seems socially distance is often described in term of respect and deference. The term of respect and different here means speaker want to keep good relationship with hearer. Showing the equivalent awareness when the other socially close is often described in terms of friendliness or solidarity (Levinson, 1983).

Yule (1996) further states that within social interaction, people generally behave as if their expectations concerning their public self-image or their face want to be respected. One's face can be categorized into two categorizations: positive face and negative face. Negative face is the basic claim to territories, personal preserves, right to non-distraction, i.e. freedom of action and freedom from imposition, while positive face is the positive consistent self-image or personally (crucially including the desire that this self-image be appreciated and approved of) claimed by interactants (Brown and Levinson, 1987). Yule (1996) states a person's negative face is the need to be independent, to have freedom of action, and not to be imposed on by others. The word "negative" does not mean "bad" just the opposite of "positive". A person's positive face is the need to be accepted, even liked by others, to be

treated as member of the same group, and to know that his or her willing is shared by others. In simple terms, negative face is the need to be independent or freedom from the imposition while the positive face is the need to be connected to other people as well as possible.

The face saving politeness theory has some strategies to save hearer's face from threat that include in the utterances. Brown & Levinson declare five strategies chosen by the speaker to save the hearer's face. First one is "bald-on record", second one is "positive politeness", third one is "negative politeness", fourth one is "off record", and the last is "saying nothing". These strategies are hierarchical forms where the first strategy until the last strategy, the FTA's will be decreased.

Every utterance certainly has function to do something. Austin (1975) believes that when speaker utter utterances to hearer, perhaps the utterances are intended to perform something (actions). This theory is called Speech Acts Theory where is grouped in some type namely; *Representative, Directive, Commisive, Expressive and Declarative*. Furthermore, Clark (2004) enlarges those five categories into 13 categories of illocutionary; *Representative, Directive, Need statement, Imperative, Embedded imperatives, Permission directives, Question directives, Hint, Commisive, Expressive, Effective, and Verdictive*.

In a definite community like in classroom, politeness is needed to be implemented since rudeness creates conflict between teacher and students, for example, a phenomenon described in Spencer-Oatey (2008). There was a Chinese teacher whose student threatred her face because of complaining her teaching strategy. The students were not satisfied with the teacher's teaching strategy where almost all of the students felt uncomfortable at that time. Similarly to the other speech communities, a process of interaction also happens by communicating with each other in the classroom. Murray (2001) states that the room here is the room that is available in

school or college where group of students are taught. Classroom is found in educational institution of all kinds, including public and private school, corporations, and religious and humanitarian organizations.

According to Gove (1961), interaction is an action that occurs as two or more objects that have an effect upon one another. There is a mutual or influence action inside of them. Moreover, Dagarin (2004) states that interaction is an action which is followed by reaction, especially, between teacher and learners, teacher and group of learners, learner and learner, as well as learners and learners.

In addition, Rivers (1987) states that an interaction is the collaborative exchange of thoughts, feelings or ideas between two or more people, resulting in a reciprocal effect on each other. Theories of communicative competence emphasize the importance of interaction as human beings using language in various contexts to "negotiate" meaning or simply stated, to get an idea out of one person's head and into the head of another person and vice versa. From very beginning of language study, classrooms should be interactive Allwright and Bailley (1991).

Besides those influences above, English classroom interaction is also influenced by the students' characteristics. The students observed in the English classroom are children. The students who are categorized as young learners are difficult to be managed. The students also are difficult in focusing the lesson because in the age 13-14, they will feel bored quickly (Harmer, 1983).

By considering the politeness strategy and the classroom interaction explained, it is obvious that discussing of politeness as strategy used by the speaker is also important in the classroom interaction. The politeness strategy can be chosen as politeness behavior to the students by teacher or by the students to their teacher as the function of the politeness strategy is to make a good relationship and also to save hearer face. Commonly, teacher wants to save the students' face in order to make a meaningful teaching and learning process

in the classroom. Carniasih (2011) states which are using appropriate politeness strategy will motivate the students. In Other word, students have good spirit when they learn English in classroom.

However, Carniasih (2011) also states that communication in the classroom interaction is influenced by the social distance, where the teacher has more power than students. This explanation will be influenced to the chosen of politeness strategy. In accordance to that situation, Seken (2007) states there are three parameters which are influenced to the chosen of politeness strategy, namely: social distance, power, and imposition. Simultaneously, those parameters will influence to the chosen of the politeness strategy, especially, in the classroom interaction.

By doing pre-observation in the eighth grade of SMP Negeri 2 Tabanan in academic year 2013/2014, it was found that in some condition there is negative face performed by students and teacher in the classroom. The conflict between teacher and students sometimes happened. Teacher sometime disappointed with students' behavior in the classroom and teacher difficult to control that condition. When the teacher feels angry to students, the students will feel scary and the process of teaching and learning will not successful. The interaction between teacher and students in classroom should be kept in a good relationship.

Because of that, the researcher wants to observe and analyze the use of politeness strategy, their function and the implication to the teaching and learning process in grade-eight of SMP Negeri 2 Tabanan in academic year 2013/2014. Here, Brown & Levinson's politeness theory (1987) and speech acts theory by Clarck (2004) were used in order to get further explanation or information about it.

Generally, the objective of this study is to find out politeness strategies used on grade-eighth EFL classroom interaction in SMP Negeri 2 Tabanan and the implication toward English teaching-learning. Moreover, the specific objectives of this study are presented as

follows; (1) to find out and classify politeness strategies used in the classroom interaction by the eighth grade EFL teacher and students of SMP Negeri 2 Tabanan. (2) to find out and analyze instructional function which are implied in the politeness strategies used by the eighth grade EFL teacher and students of SMP Negeri 2 Tabanan in EFL classroom interaction. (3) to find out and analyze the implication of the use of politeness strategies on English teaching-learning process in SMP Negeri 2 Tabanan.

RESEARCH METHODS

The design of this research was qualitative research. Qualitative research is a research which investigates the quality of relationships, activities, situations, or materials (Fraenkel and Wallen, 1993). This study was a descriptive qualitative research with a natural setting as the direct source of data with the researcher taking a role of being the key instrument (Gerring, 2007). The descriptive study can investigate the description of person, an event, a group, or an institution (Nunan, 1992).

In this study, the writer analyzed the politeness in English teaching and learning interaction in the classroom and also the implications of politeness toward teaching and learning in SMP Negeri 2 Tabanan, especially, in eighth grade in the academic year 2013/2014. The data consisted of the utterances produced by teacher and students in teaching and learning process in the classroom and also teacher and students' perception of the use of politeness, and then it was taken until the researcher found saturated data.

The researcher was the key instrument in this research. The researcher observed utterances produced by teacher and students in the classroom by recording the teaching and learning process as a video file, which was recorded by camera Nikon digital camera D3100. Besides that, the researcher was helped by using observation sheet, list and interview guide in order to get further data about the interaction between teacher and

students. Those instruments above were appropriated instruments in order to conduct descriptive study in qualitative method, where it must be helped by an instrument in observing and getting the data (Heigham & Croker, 2009).

According to Moleong (2013) to get an appropriate data, being the result of this study are reliable and valid, we need do cross-check data namely data triangulation. Added by Campbell & Fiske (2012) triangulation is an approach to research that uses a combination of more than one research strategy in single investigation. Furthermore, the writer conducted the trustworthiness of this study by concerning in four aspects; Data, Data Transcription, Technique of Data collection, Findings.

There were two main methods done in collecting the data namely observation and interview. Observation was conducted to find out the real or factual situation of teaching process. The observation was done with the help of video-records when recorded the teaching and learning process then after that note taking used to add some information for supporting the audio visual technique. The second method was interview. Interview is a way of collecting data by delivering some questions to the informants directly. The purpose of this interview was for matching the result of the observation with the opinion of informants.

The data analysis here was based on Miles-Huberman, consisting of three concept; data reduction (was done in collecting data), data display, and conclusion drawing verifications (Miles and Huberman, 1984, in Sugiyono (2013). Miles-Huberman method is ongoing activity through the investigation process rather than process. Therefore, the analysis was conducted interactively and continuously until the research problems were answered. Data Reduction; made script of recorded data and written data, chose data which was needed to answer the research problem and throw out data which was needed, identified kinds of politeness strategies, strategies of politeness, and functions of politeness. Data Display; made relation of politeness

used and English teaching-learning, displayed data in written text. The last is conclusion Drawing/Verification

The data of the present research was presented step by step. It meant that the data was explained in form of words and sentences either in deductive or inductive ways. The data analysis was presented step by step based on the research question staging in order to get a good and clear narration of the explanation of the politeness problem in this research.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

The first finding is there were some politeness strategies found to be applied at English classroom interaction in SMP Negeri 2 Tabanan. The data collection was conducted by observing nine classes randomly in grade-eight students which were handled by three teachers. After the data was collected, the writer classified the data based on the Brown & Levinson's politeness strategy theory (1987) in chapter two of this study. The data showed that 371 (32.49%) expressions were classified as Bald-on Record, 453 (39.68%) were classified as Positive Politeness, 281 (24.61%) were classified as Negative Politeness, 37 (3.24%) were classified as Off Record and there were some utterances in the conversation was not classified as all of them above, it could be called as Saying Nothing.

Data show that positive politeness dominates the use of politeness strategy in classroom interaction of eight grade students and teacher of SMP Negeri 2 Tabanan. Positive politeness becomes the dominant choice by the teacher and the students there because of the reason. The teachers choose positive politeness because they want to save the positive face of the students by exaggerate interest, or approve the students answer or idea. The common expression used to exaggerate interest, approval, and sympathy was good and very good.

Despite of that, teacher also interest to the students answer or idea. The teacher intensified interest by giving an explanation about it. In other words, by giving an explanation, it became polite,

because speaker put high attention to H. Teacher also use identity maker by using teenager language like "gahool", "FM", etc. The use of identity maker will make students more attractive in the teaching and learning process. Teacher also use seek agreement, avoid disagreement, presuppose, joke, promise, optimistic, and include the students in one activity together. Seek agreement, avoid disagreement, presuppose, promise, optimistic make the students motivation is straight forward, joke make students more interest, and by including students in one activity make students have the spirit of togetherness in learning English at that time. All of those sub-strategies save the students' positive face. The teachers choose positive politeness when they want to make a good relationship between teacher and students in the classroom which is teacher just want to claim the common ground of the students and also teacher show that they cooperate with students.

Similar with the teacher, students also dominantly use positive politeness. The students use positive politeness because they also want to save the teacher' positive face. Students just do the FTA on record plus redress to teachers' wants in the process of teaching and learning. Students show their interest or sympathy to their friend when their friend and their teacher in one situation. In here also happened the process of claiming same knowledge or point of view by students from their friends and teachers.

From the data gotten on findings which is the second rank of the dominantly politeness strategy use is bald on record. Bald on record dominantly use by the teacher in teaching and learning process. Bald on record happened because the spontaneous condition in teaching and learning process. Bald on record are chosen when the speaker wants to do FTA with maximum efficiency more than he wants to satisfy H's face. In this fact, teacher in the classroom become the leader of teaching and learning process. In classroom teacher commonly ask question to the students, give instruction, and clarify the students' idea. Because of that,

teacher often use direct imperative when they give instruction to the students. Teachers as the leader in the classroom, they lead by giving the instruction to the students. Although the teacher as leader so they use direct imperative, but the students are not satisfy with that, they do not want their teacher give direct imperative to them. Despite of that, bald on record also use for welcoming and farewells.

Students also use bald one record, but the students use bald on record when they talk with their friends. They commonly use direct imperative to their friend because they feel they stay in same level with their friend. This condition is different between student and the teachers where students believe teacher have highest level in teaching and learning process. This situation also influence by the age of the teachers and students.

Negative politeness use when the speaker wants to redress action addressed to the addressee's negative face. The teachers dominantly use negative politeness. Teachers just want to do FTA with the minimum efficiency. The teachers believe by using negative politeness can be motivate the students' negative face in teaching and learning process. In this situation, negative face commonly happened when students feel bored in the classroom. Negative face can be showed because of the teacher unable teach the students in attractive and good delivered. When the negative face is formed, teacher should be able to minimize the FTA to students. In this study teacher already use negative politeness as a strategy to redress negative face of the students.

In this study also found the use of negative politeness by students. Students use negative politeness address to the teachers' negative face. In some condition happened negative face by the teachers. Sometimes teachers feel angry or something bad condition happened between teachers and students in the classroom. Students will use negative politeness as a strategy to minimize the FTA to teacher.

Off record is done when teachers want to minimize the FTA. In this situation, teacher also dominantly use off record. Off record have purpose for decrease the intention so the student do not feel imposed by the teachers. A FTA is redressed by the use of hints that consist of some desired action of S. The use of off record by teachers is effective but teacher should be able to use appropriate expression when they utter the utterance to the students. Off record sometime is not appropriate, sometime students is very difficult in receiving it. Sometimes, the students feel bad when teacher use off record in teaching and learning process because the students do not like the indirectness in teaching and learning process.

Saying nothing used by teachers and students because of one reason. They choose it in order to make the time is efficient. They also do not do the FTA to hearer. In special case, one prefers to say nothing to save ones' face. The "say nothing strategy" at the classroom interaction was found to respond the teacher's order.

The second finding is the functions of politeness at English classroom interaction by the grade-eight students of SMP Negeri 2 Tabanan can be divided into three namely Expressive, Directive, Representative. The data showed that 253 (22.15%) expressions were classified as Expressive, 467 (40.89%) were classified as Directive, 422 (36.95%) were classified as Representative

Expressive in this research is defined as the function of politeness used to speaker expresses a psychological state. The expressive functions include greeting, appraising and apologizing, expressing disappointed about something, as well as thanking and taking leave.

It was a habit that before starting a lesson, teacher greeted the students. The greeting was done by the use of bald-on record. The expressions used for greeting were formal greeting expressions because of in formal situation for example: Good

afternoon, Good morning, and Om Swastyastu Om.

Appraising which was intended to H's positive face was more implied by teacher than students. It was occurred when the students had achievement whether having a good score or giving right answer. Related to the politeness, appraising conveyed the positive politeness. The politeness strategy used was exaggerating interest, approval, sympathy with hearer.

Expressing disappointed about something is done by the use of bald-on record and off record. The use of bald on record is less polite than off record. Thanking and taking leave is done by the use of bald-on record because they are polite in term of culture. Thanking is occurred when there is a willingness of H to do an A for S.

Directive in this research means the function of politeness to get H to do A. The directive functions can be divided into two namely giving instruction/commanding ordering and asking information/questioning.

Commanding is essential in English classroom interaction. The command used is mostly implied by teacher (who had superior power) and intended to lead the students (who have inferior power) to improve their competence and performance in English. In other words, the commanding expression used is depended on the power. Speaker who has superior power more baldly in giving instruction, at reverse, speaker who has inferior power more redress in giving instruction. Therefore, politeness strategy use is various in either bald on record or redressing. The details are presented as follows: The use of bald-on record, The use of hedges, for example please, oke, nah, well, The use of word "try", "coba", The use of "Let's", "ayo", The use of "Can", "bisa". The bald on record was only used by the superior power in the class. The instruction was in strong instruction. Asking information/ questioning in the classroom interaction were mostly in bald-on record.

Representative concerns on the illocutionary acts that derived from the essential condition of an act (the condition that defines what the act "count as"). The representative function of the politeness in the interaction is categorizing into two categorizations namely explaining material, giving information or answering question and taking order.

Almost of all explanations were explained by the teacher at the English classroom interaction. Speaker gives information to H or responds question by the use of bald on record. The motivation of the use of bald-on record is giving obvious and complete information or answer to H.

It was found that taking order was conducted into two ways, namely verbal and nonverbal. The verbal commonly involved with speaking and reading, while non-verbal needed action as a response of the order. The non-verbal frequently involved with writing and listening.

Politeness strategy used by grade eight teacher and students in the EFL classroom interaction in SMP Negeri 2 Tabanan was very influence to teaching and learning process. The politeness strategies chosen by teacher and students create the efficient interaction in the process of teaching and learning, respect communication, togetherness between teacher and students, cooperate interaction between teacher and students, and also create good condition by implementing less imposition and indirectness.

The third finding is the implication of the use of politeness by teacher and students to the EFL teaching and learning process. In the process of teaching and learning in grade eight EFL classroom interaction of SMP Negeri 2 Tabanan show that teacher and students fulfill the efficient teaching and learning in the term of interaction in communication by using bald on record and also in some condition they used saying nothing as the strategy for creating the efficient communication in the classroom interaction.

Bald on record is effective to create efficient communication between teacher and students. The efficient communication

here belongs to the Grice's maxim (1975). Speak only the truth, teacher and students talk only the factual or the truthness of the since in this case EFL classroom interaction. Don't say less than required, don't say more than is required, here teacher and students do not say more than the topic discussed at that time and also do not say less than the topic discuss. The communication relevant to the topic or lesson plan and also teacher and students try to avoid the ambiguity or clearness in the process of teaching and learning.

Respect behavior is very important in the process of teaching in learning. Teacher should be respected to the students and also the students respect to the teacher. In classroom interaction teacher and students fulfill the respect behavior by using bald on record. In interaction, teacher use greeting, thanking, and also taking leave expression. They express respect behavior in order to create good relationship between teacher and students in the classroom. Good relationship will create good teaching and learning atmosphere and good knowledge transfer from the teacher to the students.

Besides respect as a behavior that should be fulfilled in the process of teaching and learning, togetherness also is very important. Togetherness can motivate the students' learning process. Togetherness was fulfilled by using positive politeness. Similar with respect, togetherness is one aspect in order to create good relationship between teacher and students. Togetherness perform when teacher appraising the students' ideas or responses. Teacher tries to create togetherness in order to motivate the students for example by using joke, exagrate, use identity makers and intensify interest to students, etc.

Cooperate interaction is very important between teacher and students in the classroom interaction. Teacher gave an instruction to the students then students should be cooperated responding the teacher's instruction. In this case teacher use bald on record, positive politeness, negative politeness, and off record in order to make cooperation

interaction with students. Then the students use bald on record, positive politeness, and saying nothing to respond it. Cooperate can be developed based on the teacher as a leader in the classroom. Teacher can design their instruction by choosing politeness strategies at that time. Students also can respond the teacher's instruction by choosing politeness strategy.

In the classroom sometime there is negative face are formed. Negative face can be form by teacher or students. Sometimes teacher feel disappointed when cooperate interaction is avoided by students. Teacher should able to decrease imposition to students and also students should decrease imposition to the teacher. Indirect expression also is very important to minimize the FTA. Less imposition and indirectness perform by using negative politeness and off record.

All of the implication previously is much needed in the teaching and learning process of EFL classroom interaction in SMP Negeri 2 Tabanan. By implementing them the teaching and learning become meaningful and create a good atmosphere in it. The goal of teaching and learning is the process of transferring knowledge and change the students' behavior aor attitude will be successful.

Although almost the teacher and students can use politeness strategy in the interaction in the classroom, there are some situations and conditions of the interaction cannot be controlled by teacher. There are some weaknesses of the teacher. The teachers' politeness strategy is uncontrolled, teacher unable to manage their utterances belong to politeness strategy. Similary with teacher, students also difficult in choosing politeness strategy then implemented in the interaction in classroom.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

There was some politeness strategies found to be applied at English classroom interaction in SMP Negeri 2 Tabanan. The data showed that 371 (32.49%) expressions were classified as Bald-on Record, 453 (39.68%) were

classified as Positive Politeness, 281 (24.61%) were classified as Negative Politeness, 37 (3.24%) were classified as Off Record and there some utterances in the conversation were not classified as all of them above, it could be called as Saying Nothing.

The functions of the politeness used at the interaction can be divided into three namely: expressive, directive, and representative functions. The expressive functions include greeting, appraising, and apologizing, expressing disappointed about something, as well as thanking and taking leave. The directive functions meanwhile can be divided into two namely giving instruction/ commanding/ordering and asking information/questioning. The representative function of the politeness, on the other hands, is categorized into explaining material, giving information and taking order.

The implication of the politeness used at the EFL classroom interaction performs in five aspects where those aspects are very influenced in the process of teaching and learning. The five aspects are efficient teaching and learning, respect communication between teacher and students, togetherness between teacher and students, cooperating interaction between teacher and students, and the use of less imposition and indirectness expression. Those aspects can motivate students and also developing a meaningful teaching and learning process.

In learning process, there are significant influences of the politeness used at the EFL classroom interaction. In some condition, implying politeness by students and teacher only will make longer distance between teacher and students. It will make the students become not confident and not motivated in learning. Factually, mostly, students were found to be rude in speaking English because of insufficient English competence and lack understanding of politeness. Therefore, it is expected that there will be conditioning of English politeness used by the students to improve their English performance.

The teacher also should able to control the used of politeness strategies in some kind condition in the EFL classroom

interaction. Teacher should able design syllabus or lesson plan that can imply the politeness strategy in interacting in some kind activities in EFL classsroom. By design it, teacher can controlled their utterance belong to politeness strategies.

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